

Comparison of the Role of Women in Turkish Politics, Especially in the Covid-19 Pandemic, with World Women Politicians and the Role of Women in the Pandemic Process

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Abstract

The gender gap in politics continues to be the highest gender gap compared to any other field. In 2022, women around the world are still underrepresented and marginalized at all levels of

government . Women make up only 36 percent of local negotiating bodies and 26.1 percent of national parliaments. While increased women's participation in decision-making has led to more inclusive policies and service delivery, achieving equality still is a challenge as there are persistent barriers to women's equal access and participation in public life. These barriers include lack of financial resources and access to networks, discriminatory laws and institutions, and gender-based violence. Various research reports have been published on this subject. The most important research conducted with the participation of 339 companies in cooperation with TÜSİAD, TÜRKONFED and UN Women Turkey is the Effects of the COVID-19 Outbreak for Women Employees. According to the findings, it has been determined that three issues stand out in terms of female employees during the Covid-19 period: The first is housework and care responsibilities, which increased by 99%, the second increased workload with 97% remote/home working, and the third was anxiety, psychological problems with 95%. They expressed that they felt stress and burnout. UN Women has also released reports on this issue, showing that there is an increase in inequalities and that women are at risk of losing their vested rights. According to projections made by the World Economic Forum , gender equality in politics would not be achieved until 2166 if things continued at their current pace. The COVID-19 pandemic is no exception to this rule. natural disasters and manufactured crises tend to worsen pre-existing inequality.

Keywords: *Women in Turkish Politics, Covid-19 and Women in Turkish Politics, Women's Role in Pandemic, World Women Politicians and Pandemic, Covid-19, and Women's Role*

1. Introduction

Although an estimated 80 countries and territories have postponed national and local elections, at least 158 countries and territories have held elections despite concerns and restrictions related to COVID-19. Between 2020 and 2021, voter turnout is estimated to have declined in 66% of countries. Similarly, the civic and democratic spheres have shrunk: 155 countries have placed limits on freedom of assembly, and in most cases, these have been supplemented by added restrictions on civil and political rights; and 60 countries targeted freedom of expression. A

CURRENT SCIENCE

considerable number of national parliaments have reorganized their operations or reduced their workloads through remote and mixed plenary sessions, committee meetings, voting and public consultation. Virtual participation can be disadvantageous for women as it can increase their exposure to domestic violence and strengthen domestic gender roles and expectations.

While remote arrangements may remove some practical barriers to face-to-face participation for women with domestic care responsibilities and women with disabilities, for example, virtual participation can be disadvantageous for women as it can remove some practical barriers to face-to-face participation. In addition, parliaments that allow virtual participation can worsen existing political power imbalances by reducing the visibility and influence of remote participants, while giving an advantage to those physically present at meetings (those more likely to be men). Restrictions on the ability of female candidates to run political campaigns in person could have a similar effect, widening the gender gap between elite and non-elite candidates and giving an advantage to those with already set up networks, resources, and names.

2. Exposure to Online Abuse and Violence Against Women in Politics

Virtual participation and internet use are also associated with increased exposure to online abuse and violence against women in politics, which can deter women from taking part in public debates and publicly expressing their political views and wishes. This is one of the reasons why virtual participation and internet use are associated with increased exposure to online abuse and violence against women in politics. According to 2020 reports, women in political positions have been subjected to extreme levels of online harassment and harassment, not only during their tenure but also during their election campaigns and elections. In Turkey, of course, all these issues, human rights, and social rights, are under the guarantee of the state by laws. Especially within the framework of social policies, as a requirement of being a welfare state, improvements have been made in the legal legislation and mechanisms are being run in this direction. However, the facts written in the legislation sometimes do not find their counterparts in social life. The social existence of women sometimes consists of the duties they undertake (or are put on) in the family, and their main duties can be perceived as domestic care work. Our women often find it

CURRENT SCIENCE

difficult to find the balance between family and social life and work life. In other words, it is necessary to address the issue, not only within the framework of social rights.

Turkish women, who entered the parliament for the first time in 1935 with a representation rate of 4.6%, still cannot join the “men's club” even after 86 years , and the representation rate still is at 17.4%. We need more women in leading positions and active roles in every field from economy to politics, from science to technology; Only in this way can we talk about a change that spreads to all segments of society.

Despite the worldwide recognition of effective crisis management by many women leaders over the past two years, women continue to be largely excluded from most scenarios. Women are disproportionately affected by the COVID-19 pandemic and its retrospective repercussions, which are worsening existing inequalities and strengthening barriers. This includes women holding elected office, women running for office, and women voting. The purpose of this article is to raise awareness of women's political participation in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic, to gather relevant experiences, information, and good practices, and to explore how the effects of the crisis on women can best be mitigated.

Contributions will aid in the development of a report to supplement existing knowledge on the subject.

- a. *What measures can election management officials, political parties, legislators, and governments take to ensure women's equal access to elected positions?*
- b. *What kind of effects does work and taking part in a virtual parliament have on different genders?*
- c. *Has the gender-sensitive and diverse acts of your parliament been affected using remote parliamentary arrangements?*

The promotion of gender equality and the empowerment of women is publicly acknowledged as a global policy goal by both the world's countries and the leading development agencies. This recognition was made in 2015. Gender equality is not only morally and ethically correct, but it also brings positive political, economic, and social returns. As a result, actors being both the state

CURRENT SCIENCE

and non-governmental organizations have developed a wide variety of projects to this end with varying degrees of success. Political scientists have made efforts to explore what contributes to women's political representation because they are driven by the assumption that political empowerment is a necessary step on the road to gender equality in various other development measures.

According to the findings of their research, women's chances of choice are increased by various conditions. These factors include electoral gender quotas (Sacchet , 2018, [Wylie , 2018]) and proportional representation electoral systems (allowing several electoral winners) (Ahn , Kim & Kang , 2019, [Githens et al., 1994], [Matland ,] 1998], [Salmond , 2006]). An important thing to keep in mind is that the effects of these variables on increasing the number of women in political leadership are mitigated in the absence of concurrent public support for female candidates (Franceschet & Piscopo , 2008). Recent research shows that exceptional environments of conflict and political corruption scandals accompanied by public health crises as well as declines in public trust can generate public support for women's political representation in a way that public policies or institutions alone cannot.

These one-of-a-kind settings may be more conducive to female candidates, either because of increased demand for desirable qualities associated with women, or because of the constituency's focus on issues where women are viewed as women ; We suggest that the 2019-2020 Coronavirus Pandemic may have contributed to creating an environment that could foster female representation in both processes. We supply some early insights into the modern worldwide view of the coronavirus and a summary of key results from related research. These two aspects enable us to calculate the probability that the Coronavirus Pandemic will lead to helpful election outcomes for female candidates. People have a feeling that female politicians, supported by research on gender stereotypes, are more compassionate, sympathetic, honest, trustworthy, and liberal than their male counterparts ([Alexander & Andersen, 1993], [Dollar et al., 2001], Funk). , Hinojosa and Piscopo , 2019, [Huddy and Terkildsen , 1993], McDermott , 1997, Morgan, 2015). (“Light in the midst of chaos: COVID-19 and female political ...”) This is done on the assumption that voters will have a more positive impression of female candidates as they are more associated with positive qualities such as honesty and reliability. Abuse was a critical issue

both before and during the epidemic and continued to be during the epidemic. While most countries implemented strict isolation regulations (Cousins S. , 2020; Gausman J., 2020; Burki T., 2020), reports of domestic violence and abuse were increasing (Cousins S., 2020; Gausman J., 2020; Burki T., 2020). However, due to curfews, the closure of non-governmental organizations and shelters, and the fear of contracting the virus, the likelihood of abused women to move away from this scenario has been greatly reduced (Gausman J, 2020; Cousins , 2020; Balkay , 2020). Another undesirable result of curfews is an increase in the number of unwanted pregnancies and sexually transmitted diseases (Cousins S. , 2020; Burki T., 2020; Gausman J., 2020). This is because people have more difficulty accessing essential services and materials. Due to the uncertainty of the epidemic, the closure of health facilities and transportation restrictions, a sizable part of services related to sexual and reproductive health have been interrupted. As a result, these requirements were either ignored or delayed for an unknown amount of time. Intermittent or limited provision of services, or the lack of wholesale provision of certain services, is an important barrier to having safe sexual relationships, avoiding unwanted pregnancies, and protection from sexually transmitted infections (STIs). Postponing such requests will have major repercussions, such as hospitals currently understaffed and needing to select patients, and that some services are not as easily accessible as in the past. The most notable of these treatments is the elective medical termination of a pregnancy, sometimes known as abortion (Bayefsky MJ et al. 2020). This situation poses a significant danger to the health of pregnant women and their newborn children (UNICEF Turkish National Committee, 2020; Gausman J, 2020; Cousins S, 2020). Even if pregnancy is considered during the pandemic period, the possibility of becoming pregnant during this period may cause great concern for women. Due to restrictions, it is possible that pregnant women cannot meet their biological and psychological needs and may have difficulty accessing the basic pre-pregnancy and post-pregnancy care they need. In addition, the fear of contracting an illness can led to more stress and anxiety, which can directly affect a pregnant woman's health, as well as the health of her unborn child or newborn child.

3. Significant Progress on Gender Equality

7

CURRENT SCIENCE

Although much progress has been made towards gender equality, there is still a long way to go both in the rest of the world and in Turkey. Facts from around the world show that the international community needs to act together as soon as possible. There are various obstacles that need to be overcome to improve the status of women in society and in this context to advance civilizations. As of January 2015, women made up only 22 percent of the world's total legislative population. It is seen that this ratio, which was 11 percent in 1995, is gradually increasing. When it comes to employment opportunities, women are more likely to face discrimination than men. It is estimated that 700 million women get married at an incredibly early age, that is, they are under 18 years old in this marriage.

It can be shown that one out of every three women in this group, which is about 250 million women, got married before the age of 15. The dangers to women and girls are worsened when individuals are displaced against their will. Among the most significant challenges facing migrant women are gender-based discrimination, human trafficking particularly targeting women and girls, difficulties integrating into new communities, underrepresentation in political processes, and unequal access to resources and services.

Despite significant earlier efforts to improve the situation of women in Turkey, there is still work to be done. According to the 2014 Gender Equality Index of the World Economic Forum, Turkey ranks 132nd in terms of women's participation in employment and equal opportunities, and 113th in terms of political empowerment. This places Turkey in 125th place out of 142 countries. As a result of these statistics, Turkey is among the countries with high gender inequality in the Euro-Central Asian Region. Turkey was ranked 69th among 149 countries in the United Nations Development Program's (UNDP) Gender Inequality Index (GII), which measures gender inequalities in areas such as reproductive health, social empowerment, and labor force participation. According to the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) Progress Report, which has just been announced, Turkey is close to achieving its goal of gender equality in primary education; however, the proportion of girls who do not go to secondary school is surprising. One of the primary focuses of the work of United Nations organizations in Turkey is to improve the status of women in society. The following categories are the subjects of these studies:

The United Nations Gender Equality and Women's Empowerment Unit (UN Women's Unit - UN Women) Europe and Central Asia Regional Office was set up in Istanbul to work towards achieving gender equality and to cover Eastern Europe, the Balkans, Central Asia, and the Caucasus. Women's empowerment. Turkey also hosts a program unit for UN Women. The United Nations Gender Thematic Group is led by UN Women. In this context, it coordinates the formulation of policies and programs that look to ensure that the United Nations system is gender responsive and, as a result, human rights and the fair development of people of all ages.

4. Gender Responsive Budgeting

Women manages the "Gender Responsive Budgeting" project conducted within the scope of the United Nations Joint Program for the Promotion of the Human Rights of Women, conducted by the United Nations Development Program (UNDP) . , UN Women and Sabanc University. To achieve this goal, UN Women coordinates the planning and execution of ability building programs for local governments and non-governmental organisations.

Since 2004, the International Organization for Migration (IOM) has been running projects in Turkey to develop the capabilities of government agencies and their partners in civil society. These projects also aim to set up standards that will ensure long-term results in combating the exploitation of women and girls who are victims of human trafficking. By implementing its latest project , IOM Turkey wishes to contribute to both the prevention of human trafficking and the provision of human rights-based protection to victims of trafficking.

Ministries, Turkish Armed Forces, Bar Associations, and other United Nations (UN) organizations. One of the studies conducted in the GAP Region is the "Innovations in Women's Empowerment" project. Within the scope of the project, the United Nations Development Program (UNDP), the GAP Regional Development Administration and the Swedish International Development Agency (SIDA) aid hundreds of women in the Southeastern Anatolia Region to become fashion entrepreneurs.

It takes part in programs to strengthen the skills of public and non-governmental organization (NGO) employees and conducts advocacy activities to prevent twilight. In this context, training activities have been conducted, and among the beneficiaries of the training are clergy, members of the Turkish Armed Forces, members of the police force, health workers, judges and prosecutors working in family courts, and professionals. On behalf of the Ministry of Family and Social Policies. The United Nations Population Fund (UNFPA) chairs the United Nations "Women Friendly Cities" Joint Programme, which works towards achieving gender equality at the local government level. The project, the first part of which started in 2006 and has already reached a total of 12 cities, aims to improve the quality of life of millions of women and girls. It is the most comprehensive gender equality study implemented at the local level in Turkey.

5. Many Projects to Strengthen Women's Rights

In addition to initiatives conducted individually, many United Nations organizations conduct joint projects to improve the social position of women and girls. In this context, it has implemented many projects to strengthen women's rights together with UN agencies, state institutions, media, and non-governmental organizations (NGOs) in Turkey. These projects include "More and Better Jobs for Women", "Strengthening Women's Human Rights", "Women Friendly Cities" and many more. continues to work with difficulties . At a time when the international community is trying to set up sustainable development goals that will cover the period until 2030, the United Nations Organizations in Turkey are determined to join forces and make gender equality an integral part of the post-2015 sustainable development agenda. This determination comes at a time when the international community is trying to set sustainable development goals to cover the period up to 2030.

6. Election Success Chances of Female Candidates

imply that a group of nations, including the United States, Colombia, Venezuela, and Russia, have elevated levels of distrust towards their governments . More than seventy percent of

CURRENT SCIENCE

respondents in these countries showed that they do not trust the government to take care of their citizens considering the ongoing pandemic. Low public trust in government, according to previously reviewed research The government resulting from the pandemic may lead to an increase in the demand for female representation, forcing political parties to elect female candidates, and increasing the chances of female candidates' electoral success.

Besides traits or personality traits, research on gender stereotypes acknowledges that there are differences in the way male and female politicians address certain issues. Women politicians are often considered particularly adept policy makers in the "low policy" areas of education, health, and other "children and family" related issues. This contrasts with the feeling that male politicians are competent policy makers in "high policy" areas such as the economy, agriculture, employment, financial affairs, crime, and security (Herrnson , Lay , and Stokes , 2003; Lawless , 2004). Male politicians are seen as expert politicians in the "high politics" areas of the economy, agriculture, employment; (Alexander and Andersen, 1993, Herrnson , Lay and Stokes , 2003, Huddy and Terkildsen , 1993, Leeper , 1991).

Recent research has gone beyond cataloging these assumptions to show how they affect people's behavior in the voting booth. Piazza and Schneider, 2021, 2015-2016 Zika It examines whether the exceptional environment resulting from the Pandemic and the accompanying (baby) health "women's issue" brought to the fore an electoral boost for female candidates. This question is most relevant to this article. Piazza and Schneider, 2021 assess whether this increase is due to the exceptional environment.

Contemporary dynamics show that female world leaders are managing the virus in an impressive way. This could be a function of overcompetence, the disproportionate barriers women must overcome to get selected in the first place, or a tendency to seek expert advice in times of crisis. However, seeking advice from experts may also be a trend (Mahdawi , 2020, Yancey-Bragg , 2020). If these narratives do indeed upend gender stereotypes about reliability and/or competence in public health, because there are many compelling reasons to suspect so, then it is reasonable to expect female candidates to have better chances in the coming period.

In summary, the findings of this study imply that certain conditions may trigger gender stereotypes, increasing the election chances of female politicians. The 2019-2020 Coronavirus , which differs from other exceptional climates in its global reach and size We believe that the pandemic also has the potential to produce a positive outcome for women interested in running for political office. Recent opinion polls highlight widespread concerns about the public health "women's problem", as well as a general discontent with the way politicians are managing the pandemic. If contemporary public opinion is positive along with the positive media portrayal of female leaders in times of crisis, it is likely that both insiders and voters will gravitate towards female candidates. The increase in the number of women in political office has the potential to provide a crucial basis for preserving recent development achievements and achieving other goals associated with these efforts.

7. Gender Inequalities During and After the Pandemic

It is also possible that it is essential in reducing the suffering that is disproportionately distributed because of the epidemic. There is an elevated risk that gender inequalities will increase during and after the pandemic, and that the gains in human capital, economic empowerment, and voice and representation that women and girls have carefully built over the past few decades (Grown & Sánchez-Páramo , 2020). Recent reports suggest that the coronavirus is hitting economic sectors with high female employment. These repercussions may be more severe for women belonging to racial and ethnic minority groups, as they are those who face the burden of sanctions, job losses and negative impact (Kirby , 2020). There is the potential for some relief if public support for female political candidates who prove qualities of integrity and fulfill their public health duties improves because of the 2019-2020 Coronavirus Pandemic.

Women are often underrepresented in decision-making at the highest level in sectors directly affected by the COVID-19 pandemic. Despite this, women are leading effective and inclusive COVID-19 response efforts in many countries around the world. Women hold positions of power in only 21 countries worldwide,¹² but their leaders are praised for being more effective in managing the COVID-19 health crisis. Women Heads of Government in Denmark, Ethiopia,

CURRENT SCIENCE

Finland, Germany, Iceland, New Zealand, and Slovakia are known for the rapid response they have led. (“COVID-19 AND WOMEN’S LEADERSHIP: FROM AN EFFECTIVE RESPONSE TO BUILDING ...”) This response has not only included measures to 'flatten the curve' – such as incarceration measures, social isolation, and social support services – but has also been the subject of measures to prevent its spread.

By making information on women's representation in COVID-19 decision-making publicly available, it will be possible to hold governments accountable for the commitments they made in 1995 to achieve gender balance in government bodies and committees. Women's community-based organizations (CBOs) and non-governmental organizations can work together to improve women's access to information, particularly in rural areas and among populations more likely to be marginalized , such as Indigenous and minority women, lesbian, gay, bisexual, women . This is especially true in rural areas. Ensure that women and women's groups are represented and supported in the decision-making process for the COVID-19 response. Governments and funders should engage with women's groups in conducting assessments and in formulating, implementing, checking, and evaluating programs and policies.

is a coalition with support from UN Women , which includes holding a virtual knowledge sharing session in collaboration with the National Center for Disease Control in Georgia . The coalition consists of more than 400 women working at grassroots level. Building on earlier experience with the Zika virus response , UN Women has aided local women's groups in creating online and offline spaces to develop, learn and discuss public health messages targeting women, including the most marginalized. These spaces will enable women to discuss, learn and develop public health messages targeted at women. For example, UN Women in Palestine eased four meetings of women leaders and representatives of women's organizations to create a strategic space for discussion to improve coordination and access to information on gender equality issues in the national and sectoral COVID-19 response . This is done to create a strategic discussion space to improve coordination and access to information on these issues. The epidemic caused by the coronavirus continues to interfere with political processes all over the world. There were seventy-three postponed elections. Under the pretext of protecting the public's health, some parliamentary bodies have either stopped or severely restricted their work, and more than a

CURRENT SCIENCE

hundred countries have passed laws limiting individuals' rights to freedom of assembly and speech. Another advantage of the emergency was exploited by authoritarian leaders and leaders who were prone to authoritarianism to centralize authority in the executive branch.

A limited number of studies have investigated the gendered repercussions of these phenomena . For example, within political parties, disruptions in party primaries can lead male gatekeepers to choose candidates who are like them or who are part of their male-dominated social network, rather than following official election rules. This may be because male gatekeepers choose more candidates than female gatekeepers to select candidates who are like them.

It is impossible for governments, civil society groups and aid providers to continue to work to reduce these dangers and increase women's political participation both during and after the pandemic, under the assumption that nothing will change. Instead, they need to comprehensively review the electoral advice and support they provide through a gender lens and redouble their efforts to change institutions in a gender-inclusive way. The efforts of gender equality activists who struggle to support female voters and candidates at the local level and need continued support both locally and internationally can teach us a lot and we should try to learn as much as we can from them. We need a clearer view of how the epidemic is changing women's political participation so that we can systematically address the new challenges that are emerging. Election observatories run by ordinary citizens are in an excellent position to collect data like this. Observation training materials and checklists should include targeted questions about women's ability to vote and run for office. These questions should address issues such as increasing financial insecurity, caring responsibilities, and how disruptions in formal political processes affect people differently (as well as relevant subgroups of women). International election observation missions throughout the pandemic should also examine the gendered consequences of the pandemic, along with local women's rights organizations. This assessment should be made during the pandemic. Also, checking traditional and social media channels for defamation and hate speech against politically engaged women should be a priority for any monitoring effort.

EMBs), sometimes known as election watchdogs, play a key role in collecting gender-specific statistics on voter registration and turnout. They must also ensure that correct information on voting procedures continues to reach both women and men , as the International Foundation for Electoral Systems explains in more detail elsewhere . To ensure women's participation on an equal basis with men, it will be necessary to work with a range of organizations from government actors as well as civil society organizations to help close the digital gender gap. Even in the context of a pandemic, aid providers dealing directly with EMBs are capable of advocating for the systematic implementation of policies on gender quotas in place , as well as more gender-disaggregated data collection and analysis . The prevalence of gender stereotypes and patriarchal masculinity, which emphasize and convey how men should have control over women, is deeply linked to gender-based violence often perpetrated by men. This is because gender stereotypes encourage men to see themselves as superior to women. As crises and uncertainties at the individual and family level continue to worsen, those who commit acts of violence may feel an increased need to regain control over their lives and to express their frustration with more acts of violence (Angelucci & Heath , 2020), (Du , 2020; Abuhammad , 2021) . Due to all these psychological, social, economic, and individual aspects, there has been a significant decrease in women's freedom and autonomy, followed by an increase for poverty experienced by women in economic terms. Even before the pandemic, women's wages were, on average, lower than men's, and poverty rates were higher. This trend continued after the Pandemic. For example, in the OECD, 15.7% of older women lived in relative income poverty in 2016, compared to only 10.3% of older men (OECD, 2021).

However, data from the 2008 fiscal crisis and the 2014-2015 Ebola epidemic show that public policies are not enough to support women in times of crisis. Because of these factors, academic research has consistently emphasized how important it is for policy actors to take a more focused view of gender inequalities in public health emergencies (Davies and Bennett, 2016).

However, as time passes, the neologism of "self-handling" becomes increasingly ambiguous. Thus, according to intersectional feminism (Crenshaw , 1989; Costanza-Chock , 2018), the fight against female inequalities experienced by more than half of the world's population can become a virtuous process that drives a more inclusive society. This is because women experience

CURRENT SCIENCE

inequalities in more diverse areas of life than men. In the intersectional feminist approach, it is vital to analyze multiple analysis categories such as gender, race, and sexuality simultaneously (Desmond -Harris 2017). This is done to account for the interaction of different forms of inequality. The concept of intersectionality is essential for the social transformation process (Lawrence, 2017). In fact, governments should reject the idea that activities focus solely on gender divisions and instead focus their efforts on building coalitions and promoting unity. Governance must recognize how important it is to focus on who bears gender-related responsibilities and includes multiple identities. When the advantages of a gender-sensitive approach are shared in the context of an intersectional perspective with different socio-demographic characteristics, the unity of humanity will expand, and the inclusive change agenda will advance. Using this lens of observation, the Task Force's "Individuals and Society" group took initiatives to develop equality and inclusion at the intersectional and diagonal level, starting with the uniqueness of the Italian territory as its starting point (Forms 88-90).

The academic field of feminist political economy draws attention to the connections that exist between the economic, social, and political worlds. It examines the ways in which power is exercised not only through coercive methods, but also using materials and ideas, and how power relations create the institutional and ideological frameworks within which gender identities and status are produced (Rai). & Waylen , 2013). The exploration of the link between microeconomics and macroeconomics, as well as how the two interact to perpetuate and create gender inequality, is one of the defining features of the field of feminist political economy. The concept of social reproduction, which expresses the forms that underlie gendered forms of care and reproductive labor, driven and changed by the global economy, is at the center of this concept. Feminist study of political economy emphasizes not only macro-regions of political and economic power (such as international trade and finance, as well as labor regimes), but also micro-level power relations that individuals directly experience (housework, informal care economics, etc.). The role of care and social reproduction, masculine bias in macro and micro decision making, inequalities in the workplace, and the link between political resilience and insecurity are some of the issues that can be better understood with such a focus. An open question at the heart of the study of feminist political economy is how male bias affects

CURRENT SCIENCE

governance and policy making. For Elson , prejudice is more than just a matter of personal feeling; rather, it does not see laws and institutions that "act in favor of men as gender and against women as gender" (Elson , 1993, p. 238).

It is estimated that women make up two-thirds of the workforce in the healthcare industry worldwide. Although women are underrepresented in medicine, dentistry, and pharmacy globally, they make up about 85 percent of the nursing and midwifery workforce in the 104 countries for which data are available (Boniol et al., 2019[2]). In the countries that make up the OECD, women now make up almost half of the medical workforce (OECD, 2019). In addition, women make up most of the long-term care (LTC) workers. Although women are the majority of those employed in the health sector, few of those who assume senior or leadership roles in the health sector are women (Downs et al ., 2014[4]; Boniol et al ., 2019).

8. Evidence Gathered from Previous Economic and Health Crises

Companies running in a wide range of markets find themselves in a position where they have no choice but to cease or reduce their operations. This is quite likely to result in significant job losses (ILO, 2020). Evidence gathered from earlier economic and health crises shows that shocks of the size of the COVID19 pandemic often have different effects on people (Rubery and Rafferty , 2013). For example, the 2008 economic crisis was characterized by greater job losses in male-dominated sectors (especially construction and manufacturing), as well as an increase in the number of hours worked by women, especially in the early years of the crisis (Şahin, Song , & Hobijn , 2012[18]; OECD, 2012).). According to Périvier (2014) and Périvier (2014), during the recovery period men's employment recovered faster than women's employment . On the other hand, data from economic crises caused by infectious diseases often point to worse outcomes for women.

9. A Gender Balance Between Voters

CURRENT SCIENCE

Experimental research reveals that voters' perceived procedural legitimacy for electing a government increases when there is a gender balance among those who choose the outcome (Clayton, O'Brien , and Piscopo Reference Clayton, O'Brien , and Piscopo2019). Citizens may reflect these normative concerns. Two other arguments can be made in favor of descriptive representation . The first is the symbolic argument that the addition of those previously excluded from institutions signifies their equality (Phillips Reference Phillips1998). In addition, it is essential that individuals “see” themselves represented in their government. Greater female representation has been shown to increase women's political knowledge (Dassonneville and McAllister Reference Dassonneville and McAllister2018), political debate among young women (Wolbrecht and Campbell Reference Wolbrecht and Campbell2017), and girls expected political participation (Dassonneville and McAllister Reference). Dassonneville and McAllister2018) (Campbell and Wolbrecht Reference Campbell and Wolbrecht2006). Representation also has policy implications. Scholars of feminism make connections between descriptive and substantive representation (acts of representatives). “There are special needs, interests, and concerns arising from women's experiences and these will be inadequately addressed in a male-dominated politics.” (Phillips Reference Phillips1998, 66).

10. Conclusion

There is a link between the presence of women and the substantive representation of interests or problems, but the evidence for this link is mixed (for example, Homola Reference Homola2019). We recognize that this relationship is not perfect, as representation changes based on several circumstances , including the nature of the situation, the institutions involved, and the diversity of women in political office (Childs and Lovenduski Reference Childs). , Lovenduski , Waylen , Celis , Kantola and Laurel Weldon2013). On the other hand, there is a correlation between the presence of women in positions of power where decisions are made and better outcomes for women. Female representatives are more likely than men to act on behalf of women (Annesley et al., Reference Annesley, Engeli, Gains, and Resodihardjo2014 ; Catalano Reference Catalano2009; Celis Reference Celis2013; Taylor-Robinson and Heath Reference Taylor-

CURRENT SCIENCE

Robinson and Heath2003; Wangnerud Reference Wangnerud2009). This is because female representatives see their gender as a constituency (Childs Reference Childs 2004). This memo keeps track of the sexual orientation of both cabinet ministers and expert advisers who attend daily briefings . The legislative space was where the work of representation first began but has since expanded to include institutions outside the legislature such as executive branches, agencies, political parties, and social organizations (Annesley , Gains and Franceschet Reference Annesley , Gains and Franceschet2019; Bergqvist Reference Bergqvist1999; Breitenbach Reference Breitenbach1981; McBride and Mazur Reference McBride and Mazur2010; Murray Reference Murray2008). Saward's According to his argument (cited in Saward2010), representation can take place in a variety of settings, outside legislatures and even outside institutions and official politics. These briefings are the public face of government decision-making on COVID-19 and therefore have strong symbolic repercussions for women's representation. In addition, although the briefings do not clearly find the people responsible for policy, they likely are priorities that are considered throughout government decision-making processes. Considering the gender implications of the pandemic, it is also vital to consider the descriptive portrayal of women in the coronavirus outbreak. This includes incorporating women's economic life into the core of pandemic response and recovery strategies, as well as economic and social policies that take gender dynamics into account . As of March 31, 105 countries have successfully enacted fiscal response packages totaling \$4.8 trillion in the United States. As of April 3, 2019, a total of 106 countries have begun or amended efforts to improve social protection and employment opportunities in response to COVID-19. Social benefits, also known as non-contributory transfers, are the most often used tool among these packages. It is important that sectors that employ significant numbers of women and experience disruptions in their supply chains have access to sufficient loans, credits, and grants to keep their female workforce. This includes removing barriers to women's full participation in economic activities, equal pay and equal opportunities, social protection schemes that consider existing prejudices, funding for self-employed women, and mechanisms to encourage women to start their own business. As a result, current social protection programs do not cover a wide enough audience.

Many women are likely to be excluded, as access to safety nets is largely dependent on formal participation in the workplace . More studies are needed on this subject for Turkish literature.

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